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Redesign and Optimization of Thermal Protection System for Atmospheric Reentry

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Background

Heat shields are essential for the safety of reentry vehicles [1-2]

Phenolic Impregnated Carbon Ablator [3-4]
(NASA Ames Research Center)

Virgin ablator → Charring ablator + Pyrolysis gas

Efficiency

Mathematical Model for charring ablator

Conservation of Mass :

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_g}{\partial x} = -\frac{d\rho_s}{dt}$$

Conservation of Energy :

$$\rho_s c_{ps} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-k \nabla T) + \dot{m}_g c_{pg} \nabla T = (h_g - h_s + h_p) \frac{\partial \rho_s}{\partial t}$$

Kinetic model of pyrolysis reaction :

$$\frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} = A_i (1 - \alpha_i)^{n_i} \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{\hat{R}T}\right)$$

Boundary Condition:

$$-(k \nabla T)_w = q_{cw} - q_{cw} \frac{h_w}{h_r} - 0.58 \cdot \dot{m}_g \cdot (h_r - h_w) - \varepsilon \sigma (T_w^4 - T_{amb}^4)$$

Thermal reradiation from material surface:

$$r_{rerad} = \int_0^{t_{all}} \varepsilon \sigma (T_w^4 - T_{amb}^4) / q_{cw} dt$$

Heat dissipation by heat blocking effect:

$$r_{\psi} = \int_0^{t_{all}} 0.58 \cdot \dot{m}_g \cdot (h_r - h_w) / q_{cw} dt$$

Heat dissipation by hot wall effect:

$$r_{hw} = \int_0^{t_{all}} h_w / h_r dt$$

Heat absorption by material heat capacity:

$$r_c = \int_0^{t_{all}} \int_0^l (\rho_s h_s)_t dx / q_{cw} dt$$

Heat dissipation by pyrolysis:

$$r_p = \int_0^{t_{all}} \int_0^l h_p \cdot (\rho_s)_t dx / q_{cw} dt$$

Mass ejection of pyrolysis gases:

$$r_g = \int_0^{t_{all}} (\dot{m}_g h_g)_w / q_{cw} dt$$

**Energy
accommodation
mechanisms**

Thermal behavior of charring ablator

Lightweight Carbon Phenolic Ablator

Boundary Conditions:

Surface: $q_{cw} = 1\text{MW/m}^2$ $hr = 21.34\text{MJ/kg}$ $t_{all} = 90\text{s}$

Bottom: adiabatic and $T \leq 450\text{K}$

$h_1 = 28.312\text{mm}$

Areal density = 7.729kg/m^3

(obtained by Nelder Mead Method)

Redesign of thermal protection structure

Effect of different energy accommodation mechanisms

Densities of the virgin ablator and the insulator are **273kg/m³** and **144kg/m³**, respectively [5, 7].

Thermal conductivity [5-6]

Redesign of thermal protection structure

$h_1 = 15\text{mm}$; $h_2 = 12.78\text{mm}$
 Areal density = 5.937kg/m^3

Temperature and pyrolysis degree profile at different time

The areal density of hybrid TPS is reduced by **23.19%** compared with the original design.

Summary

- A mathematical model for charring ablators has been established.
- Energy accommodation mechanisms of lightweight carbon phenolic ablator has been analyzed.
- A hybrid TPS has been developed which could improve the performance of TPS compared with the traditional design composed of single material.

References

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Thank you for your attendance

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